

International Journal of Accounting Finance and Management Sciences

ISSN: 2785-9010

Vol 10, Issue 02, Oct 2025

Received: 06 August 2025 Revised: 19 Sept 2025 Accepted: 10 Oct 2025

A Bibliometric Analysis of Job Satisfaction and Burnout Among Healthcare Staffs

Aamer Saleem ✉¹, Mahiswaran A/I Selvanthan²

Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities

Universiti Teknologi Malaysia

Correspondence: saleem.aamer@graduate.utm.my

Abstract:

Healthcare professionals, the primary warriors, are emotionally exhausted because of the global health crisis; thus, understanding burnout and job satisfaction is imperative. The purpose of this study is to investigate the factors that contribute to burnout and job satisfaction among healthcare workers. A bibliometric analysis was adopted to evaluate global trends by narrowing job burnout and job satisfaction research on the healthcare sector. Out of 3706 articles assessed, the analysis included 2159 articles from the Scopus database, the largest research database covering a wide range of subjects compared to others. The ten period from 2016 to 2025 was selected to unbiasedly assess research trends both before and after the pandemic. The VOSviewer was employed to perform the analysis and address the research questions. The results indicate that the COVID-19 pandemic has heightened the need for mental health and burnout research among healthcare professionals, with a 28% increase. Research on occupational health, satisfaction, and patient safety before COVID-19 has shifted to workplace violence, stress, and resilience, with increased burnout and job satisfaction. The USA, China, Australia and UK, are the leading countries with high research publications. Thus, understanding burnout and job satisfaction is crucial for managers and policymakers, as effective policies and support initiatives can boost satisfaction and reduce burnout.

Keywords—; Global health crisis; Job satisfaction, Workplace violence; Burnout

Introduction

Healthcare professionals have a critical role in maintaining and enhancing the health and well-being of individuals (Chaudhuri et al. 2021). Their role is essential in improving the health and well-being of individuals across the nation. Healthcare workers, including doctors, nurses, and allied health professionals, provide direct patient care, and their significance cannot be overstated, regardless of their position (O'Brien et al. 2017). They are the foundation of individuals' health, offering crucial services such as disease prediction, treatment, prevention, as well as societal health. However, despite their significance, healthcare workers face a multitude of stressors that affect their well-being. These stress levels, although common to employees in any organization, are often intensified in healthcare settings (Gray et al. 2019). Stress in healthcare is influenced by long working hours, unreasonable working conditions, sleep disorders, a lack of work-life balance, low pay, limited promotion opportunities, professional responsibility, dealing with daily illness and death, and a sense of failure (Klein et al. 2011; Kelly et al. 2020).

This stress, particularly when prolonged, often leads to burnout, which is a significant concern for healthcare employees. The COVID-19 global health crisis has worsened this situation, intensifying work stress experienced by healthcare professionals (Ardebili et al. 2021). Burnout is a progressive psychological response that gradually develops over time as a result of continuous workplace stress and overwork, leading to reduced effectiveness and personal accomplishment (Edu-Valsania et al. 2022). As burnout takes hold, it leads to decreased job performance, increased errors, reduced patient satisfaction, and increased turnover (Garcia et al. 2019). It affects the well-being of the employee as well as organizational performance. It was also reported that job performance and patient care service of the hospital workers is also influenced by emotional and cultural intelligence (AlUbaidi et al. 2020; Porkodi et al. 2022).

Job satisfaction, in addition to burnout, plays a substantial role in the overall performance of healthcare employees. As an emotional factor, job satisfaction significantly influences employee performance, turnover, and organizational commitment (Platis et al. 2015). Similar to burnout, job dissatisfaction in healthcare workers impacts patient satisfaction, turnover, and the quality of treatment provided (Chang et al. 2017). Job satisfaction is influenced by several elements, the most important being satisfaction with managers and supervisors, satisfaction with job content, and satisfaction with coworkers (Rad and De Moraes 2009).

Understanding the relationship between burnout and job satisfaction is crucial because both factors significantly affect organizational commitment, employee retention, and organizational performance (Porkodi and Haque 2012). Furthermore, a strong relationship has been found between stress and burnout, with burnout negatively impacting job satisfaction (Tziner et al. 2015). Thus, examining these two variables in combination is essential for improving work productivity, patient care, and addressing staff attrition and turnover rates (Khamisa et al. 2015). The post-pandemic period has further complicated these issues for healthcare workers. The increased workload, emotional stress, high infection risks, and anxiety have added new layers to the challenges faced by healthcare professionals (Leo et al. 2021). This growing complexity underscores the urgent need for studies on burnout and job

satisfaction to better understand the current dynamics and provide effective solutions (Zhou et al. 2022). Given the growing concern over emotional exhaustion among healthcare workers, the primary objective of this study is to explore emotional factors such as burnout and job satisfaction, emphasizing their importance in enhancing healthcare quality, retaining employees, and promoting sustainability post-pandemic. Previous studies have explored related factors such as burnout, compassion fatigue, compassion satisfaction (van Mol et al. 2015; Lluch et al. 2022), burnout and well-being (Johnson et al. 2017; Selič-Zupančič et al. 2023), stress (Friganović et al. 2019), and job satisfaction (Lu et al. 2019; Dubale et al. 2019). However, few studies have addressed burnout and job satisfaction among healthcare workers (Doolittle 2015), its relevance is limited by significant changes in the healthcare context.

While burnout and job satisfaction are critical areas in healthcare research, technological advancements and the COVID-19 pandemic have notably altered the dynamics of the literature. Despite the acknowledged social significance of healthcare development, there has been no systematic literature review on burnout and job satisfaction. Moreover, the growing body of literature has not been comprehensively evaluated through bibliometric techniques, resulting in gaps regarding research themes, trends, and geographic contributions.

This study addresses bibliometric analysis and offering an overview of the conceptual and intellectual frameworks in research on healthcare workers' job satisfaction and burnout. The study focuses on bibliometric analysis and current trends, leaving the systematic literature review for future research. Through the mapping of conceptual and intellectual structures within the field, bibliometric analysis offers a methodical way to address this problem (Salleh et al. 2023; Ali et al. 2023; Fatima et al. 2024). This study is driven by the need for a comprehensive performance analysis that integrates both qualitative and quantitative insights, addressing gaps in theme evolution, geographic contributions, and research impact. Given the surge in research output during and after the pandemic, which has provided researchers access to a larger dataset for analysis, this is especially crucial. Using the leading research database, the Scopus Database, this study used bibliometric analysis to explain historical trends and prospects while keeping the phenomenon of interest important. The main themes were 'job burnout', 'job satisfaction', and 'healthcare'. Compared to the Web of Science and other databases, the Scopus database is considered the largest for citations and abstracts covering a broad range of topics (Salleh et al. 2023). This study used all possible keywords related to the study theme using a query search string, field codes, and Boolean logic appropriately. Furthermore, to fairly evaluate research trends prior to and following the pandemic, a nine-year timeframe from 2016 to 2025 was chosen. This time range helps to assess the studies published before and after the pandemic fairly and equally.

Thus, the main objective of the study is to explore performance, global trends, influential factors, relevant themes and topics, geographical trends, and key contributors to the research on job burnout and job satisfaction among healthcare employees using scientific mapping. The analysis has been carried out by selecting 2159 papers from the Scopus database, published between 2016 and 2025, with predefined search keywords. The identified research gaps were used to develop the following research questions, which serve as a roadmap for the current study.

RQ1. How have the articles on burnout and job satisfaction among healthcare employees progressed over time?

RQ2. How have the trends and themes in the research on burnout and job satisfaction of healthcare employees evolved?

RQ3. What are the most significant countries, and how has their collaboration contributed to this research?

RQ4. How has the research on burnout and job satisfaction among healthcare employees impacted the academic and scientific community?

Literature Review:

The study's theoretical foundation builds on principles established by previous research on burnout and job satisfaction among healthcare workers (Cetinkaya et al. 2017; Adamopou-los 2022). It is anchored in theories related to these two factors, particularly the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI) model, one of the most widely used frameworks for measuring burnout (Soares et al. 2023). This model focuses on three dimensions: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. By providing a comprehensive framework, the MBI model supports the current research in understanding how the pandemic influenced burnout and job satisfaction among healthcare professionals.

Burnout among healthcare professionals has been extensively studied, with research highlighting factors such as gender, work title, specialization, and workload, particularly during pandemics (Jia et al. 2023; Dinibutun et al. 2023). Women have been reported to experience higher stress levels than men, while men demonstrate stronger associations between burnout and emotional acting (Akerstrom et al. 2023; Kroft 2020; Soumyaja et al. 2022). Nurses, in particular, are identified as experiencing greater stress than other healthcare workers, with younger, less experienced nurses bearing a heavier workload and being especially vulnerable to burnout (Tziner et al. 2015; Lee 2019). Additionally, compassion fatigue significantly affects performance, turnover, and patient care (Hameed et al. 2023). Physical symptoms like fatigue and anxiety further exacerbate burnout (Khamisa et al. 2017; Larasati and Aryanto, 2020). While collaboration and autonomy can improve overall well-being, burnout remains a critical metric for assessing healthcare systems. Research has increasingly emphasized employee well-being in the context of burnout syndrome (Kroft 2020; Ashton-James and McNeilage 2022).

Job satisfaction, closely linked to burnout, reflects the emotional and behavioral dimensions of an employee's attitude and performance at work. Studies indicate that dissatisfaction among healthcare professionals contributes to high turnover rates, with 40% of employees likely to leave their jobs (Abate and Mekonnen 2021). Conversely, satisfied employees demonstrate greater loyalty to their organizations (Vuong et al. 2021). Among nurses, workplace dissatisfaction is often associated with low wages, high workloads, and diminished work-life balance, which further increase stress (Lee 2019; Akerstrom et al. 2023). However, factors such as intrinsic job meaning and supportive coworker relationships have been shown to enhance job satisfaction and overall well-being (Ashton-James and

McNeilage 2022). Addressing job satisfaction and mitigating psychosocial risks are essential for promoting workplace health, productivity, and organizational performance (Adamopoulos 2022).

Generally, burnout and job satisfaction are strongly interconnected, sharing a negative and inverse relationship. Burnout is a significant predictor of low job satisfaction (Moscu et al. 2022). Gender plays a moderating role in the indirect effects of deep and surface acting on these variables (Soumyaja et al. 2022). While emotional labor among nurses has limited direct impact, studies reveal a moderately strong negative correlation between burnout and job satisfaction (Lee 2019). Technology use has emerged as a positive factor, enhancing job satisfaction and organizational advocacy, particularly among rural medical practitioners (Terry and Mathews 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic has amplified the challenges of burnout and job dissatisfaction, especially among nurses (Galanis et al. 2023). Additional factors like workplace bullying and violence further contribute to burnout, while social support and organizational justice help mitigate these effects and improve productivity (Bashir and Hanif 2018; Cao et al. 2023).

Although several bibliometric analyses have been conducted in related areas, research specifically addressing burnout and job satisfaction among healthcare employees remains limited, underscoring the relevance of the current study. Between 1980 and 2015, studies on hospital chaplain burnout, compassion fatigue, and job satisfaction were reviewed (Doolittle 2015; van Mol et al. 2015). However, none of these reviews addressed job satisfaction in healthcare post-pandemic. Unlike empirical reviews, bibliometric studies provide valuable insights into the evolution, key themes, and trends over time. For instance, previous studies have examined global trends in burnout among healthcare professionals, some focusing on specific roles such as nurses (de Oliveira et al. 2021), others exploring region-specific patterns (Barragán Martín et al. 2020), while some have taken a more general approach without sector-specific focus (Carvalho et al. 2023) or concentrated on a limited timeframe, such as pandemic-related trends from 2020 to 2022 (Ulfa et al. 2022; Lluch et al. 2022). Selič-Zupančič et al. (2023) covered 2011–2021 but focused on just 15 studies. Other bibliometric studies have examined related themes, such as compassion fatigue (Sweileh 2020), job insecurity (Prado-Gascó et al. 2021), organizational commitment (de Las Heras-Rosas et al. 2021), and job satisfaction (Saha et al. 2024). By addressing the lack of systematic literature reviews or bibliometric analyses in this specific focus, this study makes a significant and original contribution to the literature.

Methodology

In this study, the methodology for the bibliometric analysis was designed based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines, which support minimizing bias and enhancing transparency through a systematic research framework (Page et al. 2021; Rauf et al. 2024). The PRISMA framework was adapted for both reporting and screening purposes in this study, ensuring clarity and precision in the study selection and analysis process. To achieve the research objectives and effective results, Scopus was employed as the data source (Saha et al. 2024). Scopus was chosen for this study primarily due to its broader coverage compared to Web of Science (WOS), which provides

valuable academic data but has a more limited scope, or Google Scholar, which lacks a robust quality control procedure (Ali et al. 2023). Scopus provides broader, multidisciplinary coverage, particularly in healthcare research, making it a better fit for analyzing the intersection of job satisfaction, burnout, and COVID-19 (de-la-Fuente- Robles et al. 2022). Furthermore, Scopus has been widely used in multiple bibliometric studies (Sweileh 2020; Ulfa et al. 2022), demonstrating its reliability for research in this domain. While WOS is also comprehensive, it does not offer the same extensive coverage across interdisciplinary fields, particularly those related to healthcare and social sciences, further reinforcing the choice of Scopus as the primary data source (Ali et al. 2023).

The bibliometric data collected from this source provided significant insights essential for analyzing the relationship between the impact of COVID-19 on job satisfaction and burnout among healthcare employees. In this context, bibliometric analysis proved valuable for both quantitative and qualitative evaluations, helping to identify key contributors, research trends, shifts in boundaries, and evolving themes. The results of this analysis could guide potential future research directions in this field (Huang et al. 2020). For the analysis, VOSviewer, was used. VOSviewer is providing a comprehensive integration of all primary bibliometric analysis techniques for scientometric and bibliometric research (Urkude and Sahoo, 2024). VOSviewer supported Scopus data files primarily for network mapping (Ding and Yang 2022). This feature ensured that all steps from data collection to analysis could be conducted within a single tool, streamlining the process and improving the accuracy of results. The following search string was finalized for use in the Scopus database:

TITLE-ABS-KEY (((satisfaction OR fulfillment OR fulfilment OR work* satisfaction* OR job* engagement* OR occupational* satisfaction* OR employee* satisfaction*) AND (burnout OR exhaustion OR stress)) AND ((healthcare OR hospital OR medical OR clinic OR paramedical OR health* professional* OR medical* staff*)) AND (employee OR professional OR worker OR nurse OR doctor OR clinician))) AND PUBYEAR > 2016 AND PUBYEAR < 2025 AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English"))).

The search for study articles was conducted on July 31, 2025, guided by the predefined search terms and inclusion/exclusion criteria. This search initially resulted in 3706 articles published in journals, conferences, and book chapters then 2159 papers selected which published in journals and limit language with English. These records were downloaded as CSV data files, which can be imported into various programs, such as R and Excel, for further analysis. During the data cleaning stage, the PRISMA guidelines were followed to ensure the selection of the most relevant studies for the analysis. This methodology is structured in three key phases: (1) identification of data sources and data gathering; (2) screening and extraction of essential information; and (3) inclusion of articles for analysis. By adhering to these phases, the study aligns with best practices in bibliometric research, ensuring methodological rigor. To meet the research objectives, the search was narrowed down using the following inclusion criteria: literature spanning from 2016 to 2025; and articles written in the dominant language, English. This stage resulted in a total of 2159 articles. In addition to the inclusion criteria, exclusion criteria were applied. These included eliminating articles that were not written in English, were published before 2016, were not relevant to the topic, or were not published in peer-reviewed journals. This screening process ensured the selection of articles with high academic standards aligned with the study's

objectives. To maintain data integrity and quality, the dataset was reviewed for completeness, and duplicate documents were identified by examining article abstracts to ensure the dataset was free from errors. Ultimately, 2159 articles were selected for bibliometric analysis on the impact on job satisfaction and burnout among healthcare employees. Moreover, the selected records were assessed for missing information using MS Excel, with any gaps manually filled in and saved as *.csv files for the next stage of analysis. Quantitative data, such as publication years, was imported into Excel for graph visualization, while VOSviewer was used for keyword network analysis.

Findings and Discussion

Annual Scientific Production

The analysis of annual scientific production (RQ1) shows significant annual growth in research on burnout and job satisfaction among healthcare employees, reflecting increased awareness of these critical issues in the sector. Several factors have contributed to the increase in publications over time. This increased focus is likely linked to the social and economic effects of the pandemic, which included heavier workloads, emotional stress, and concerns over personal safety. The growing acknowledgment of mental health, especially in high-stress professions like healthcare, has likely stimulated scholarly interest in this area. A visual representation of the annual distribution of publications among the selected reviewed papers is provided in Fig. 1 to address RQ1.

Fig. 1 Annual distribution of publications

Conceptual Analysis

In response to RQ2, the conceptual structure has been assessed for the selected articles related to burnout and job satisfaction among medical professionals. Generally, word relationships in the bibliometric database are explored within the conceptual framework. This was accomplished by analyzing the titles and keywords of the selected publications. The analysis aims to evaluate the level of knowledge about the research domains or topics and identify the research topics that are most commonly discussed. Eventually, the selected studies comprise 390 author keywords and 520 Keywords Plus, derived from frequently occurring terms or phrases in article references’ titles but not the article’s title.

Fig. 2 Word cloud generated from article titles

Figure 2, a word cloud generated from the titles of the articles, shows that the most significant terms used in the articles are 'burnout', 'satisfaction', 'job', 'healthcare', 'professionals', 'COVID-19', 'compassion', and 'stress'. In addition, while assessing the title terms, it was found that most of the top keywords were in the titles of the articles. While assessing the abstract, it was found that 'job satisfaction' is the dominant term followed by 'healthcare professionals' and 'workers', 'job burnout', 'compassion satisfaction', and 'pandemic'. The new terms that occurred more in the abstract are 'Maslach burnout', 'life satisfaction', and 'mental health'. The top 10 keywords are depicted in Fig. 3, with the top 10 authors' keywords on the left and the top 10 abstract keywords on the right-hand side graph.

Fig. 3 Top 10 keyword frequency

Evolution of Trends and Themes

A response to 'RQ3' is provided by assessing the development of the themes and trends from the selected study's topics examined in this section. For the analysis, the evolution of the top 10 keywords over the past nine years is evaluated by identifying the frequency of these keywords in each year. Figure 4 presents the top 10 authors' keywords and their frequency over time. While terms such as 'burnout' and 'job satisfaction' gradually increased over time before 2019, they have seen a rapid increase post-2019.

Fig.4 Co-occurrence network with keyword plus

As depicted in Fig. 4, the terms 'human' and 'burnout,' are highly co-occurring in the keyword plus, which is also interconnected with 'professionals,' 'cross-sectional studies,' and 'questionnaires.' The terms 'Job satisfaction' are associated with 'male,' 'female,' 'adult,' and 'middle-aged.' The term 'COVID-19' is associated with 'healthcare professionals,' 'empathy,' and 'personal satisfaction'.

Fig. 5 Top 5 Journals of Nursing Job satisfaction overtime

Figure 5 presents the top five journals of nursing job satisfaction overtime. While terms such as 'burnout' and 'job satisfaction' gradually increased overtime after Covid-19 to 2025.

Social Structure Analysis

This section discusses a simple analysis of the authors, their affiliations, and the countries involved in the specific topic of the research study to respond to RQ4. Around 592 authors participated in the assessment of job satisfaction and burnout among paramedical workers. These authors belong to a wide range of 37 countries around the world.

Documents by country or territory

Compare the document counts for up to 15 countries/territories.

Fig. 6 Country-wise distribution of selected studies

Figure 6 shows that the countries participated in the research on job satisfaction and burnout among par- amedical employees, including the USA, China, Australia, UK and other countries respectively. More specifically, between the years 2016 and 2025, the USA ranked in either of the top two places. The findings show that job satisfaction and burnout among para- medical workers are receiving increasing global attention, with China and the USA leading research efforts.

This broad institutional and geographic participation reflects the increasing global awareness of the significance of job satisfaction and burnout research. Institutions worldwide are contributing more to healthcare workers' well-being research due to evolving challenges like COVID-19 and rising workforce pressures. Figure 7 shows the top 10 affiliations of authors in selected studies with universities.

Documents by affiliation

Compare the document counts for up to 15 affiliations.

Fig. 7 Institutional-wise distribution of selected studies

Figure 7 shows top list institute of research worldwide and research from Monash University examines the role of shared experiences and peer support in addressing occupational burnout, providing valuable insights into interventions that promote a positive work environment. Similarly, studies from Shandong University investigate the impact of work- place verbal violence on healthcare professionals and propose training interventions to mitigate its effects, highlighting the need for organizational-level strategies.

Intellectual Structure Analysis

This section presents the impact and influence of research on job burnout and satisfaction among healthcare workers on the academic and research communities, addressing RQ4. Remarkably, these selected articles achieved an average citation rate of per document and included an average of references, demonstrating the significant impact of this research on the academic community. The result indicates that studies on healthcare workers' job satisfaction and burnout have had a significant impact on the academic community. The increase in citations, particularly after 2020, reflects the growing importance of healthcare workers' mental health, influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic and increasing strains on healthcare systems. The significant reference count and high average citation rate further emphasize how these studies are intertwined with shifting societal, economic, and cultural contexts, highlighting the relevance of healthcare workers' well-being and burnout in the evolving healthcare sector. Figure 8 revealed the top authors worldwide contributing new knowledge in job satisfaction and job burnout in healthcare sector.

Documents by author

Compare the document counts for up to 15 authors.

Fig. 8 Top authors of the studies

Figure 8 shows the top authors worldwide contributing new knowledge in job satisfaction and job burnout in healthcare sector. A significant component in determining the quality and impact of articles within the research community is the number of citations they receive. Citation counts reflect how often an article has been cited by other academics. In this bibliometric analysis, both global and local citations are considered. The 1st top author is Labrague who published approximately 19 articles and Estabrooks is 2nd top list author with 9 articles.

Fig. 9 Co-citation network analysis

Figure 9 Co-citation analysis reveals the connections between academic publications by examining how frequently they appear together in other studies. It helps identify important research areas, essential works, and the development of topics within the field, such as healthcare workers’ job satisfaction and burnout. The increase in co-citation frequency after 2020 reflects a cultural change as the pandemic’s impact on

healthcare systems around the world has made healthcare workers' mental health a top priority. It increases publications and co-citations worldwide.

Conclusion

This study highlights the importance of addressing burnout and job satisfaction in the healthcare sector, emphasizing the need for workforce resilience programs and positive organizational culture. The surge in publications post-2019, influenced by COVID-19, highlights the importance of prioritizing mental health and addressing burnout among healthcare professionals, benefiting the scientific community. Post-2019 publications underscore the need to prioritize mental health and address burnout among healthcare professionals, highlighting the significant annual growth in research on this topic. An analysis of conceptual structures reveals a correlation between burnout, stress, resilience, compassion fatigue, and work satisfaction. In addition, positive (empathy, well-being) and negative (distress, anxiety) elements are highlighted. Job satisfaction is impacted by workplace support, emotional labour, compassion, and mindfulness and these factors need more research. However, a more in-depth data analysis is needed to fully substantiate this connection. Research shows that positive and negative elements affect job satisfaction through workplace support, emotional labour, compassion, and mindfulness.

Further, research on stress, resilience, and burn-out among healthcare personnel is growing, with leading nations like the US, China, and UK, conducting studies. Research on burnout and job satisfaction in health-care shows worldwide collaboration, with 9% having a single author and 15% including international collaboration, with leading nations including the US, China, UK, and Australia. Healthcare research significantly impacts burnout and job satisfaction, with influential authors addressing workplace stress reduction, professional fulfillment, and COVID-19 effects on burnout and compassion fatigue. The study explores burnout and job satisfaction among healthcare employees, emphasizing the importance of managing it to retain and improve patient care post-pandemic. Thus, implementing employee resilience programs, supporting initiatives, creating a positive work environment, enhancing well-being, and providing robust organizational support can optimize the emotional factors of healthcare employees.

The findings of this study have significant implications for various stakeholders involved, including healthcare organizations, hospital managers, healthcare professionals such as doctors and nurses as well as patients. It facilitates the development of evidence-based practices for enhancing effective and resilient healthcare systems. By developing a positive work environment, identifying and implementing policies, and considering employee well-being, healthcare managers can improve employee satisfaction, reduce stress, anxiety, and depression, thereby decreasing burnout and the intention to leave. This will ultimately improve patient safety, healthcare quality, and organizational performance. In order to improve patient care, professional fulfilment, and general well-being, health-care professionals can experience less burnout and compassion fatigue in a supportive and healthy work environment. Patients benefit from better care, increased patient safety, and a more sympathetic healthcare experience when healthcare workers are more resilient. Healthcare workers' families benefit from improved emotional well-being,

work-life balance, and enhanced patient care, while patients' families benefit from improved stress management and high-quality care. Policymakers can inspire and motivate workers by instituting new practices and initiatives, especially in times of crisis and disasters. Thus, this research offers practical insights for healthcare organizations seeking to optimize their workforce during and after global health crises, contributing to the development of evidence-based practices for improving healthcare systems' effectiveness and resilience.

References

Abate, H.K., Mekonnen, C.K.: Job satisfaction and associated factors among health care professionals working in public health facilities in Ethiopia: a systematic review. *J. Multidiscipl. Healthc.* 14, 821–830 (2021)

Adamopoulos, I.P.: Job satisfaction in public health care sector, measures scales and theoretical background. *Eur. J. Environ. Public Health* 6(2), 0116 (2022)

Akerstrom, M., Sengpiel, V., Hadžibajramović, E., Carlsson, Y., Graner, S., Andersson, O., Jonsson, M., Naurin, E., Veje, M., Wessberg, A., Linden, K.: The COPE staff study: study description and initial report regarding job satisfaction, work-life conflicts, stress, and burnout among Swedish maternal and neonatal healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Int. J. Gynecol. Obstet.* 162, 989 (2023)

Ali, A., Ramakrishnan, S., Faisal, F., Akram, T., Salam, S., Rahman, S.U.: Bibliometric analysis of finance and natural resources: past trend, current development, and future prospects. *Environ. Dev. Sustain.* 25(11), 13035–13064 (2023).

AlUbaidi, A., AlLawati, J., AlZadjali, S., AlBalushi, M., Porkodi, S.: Impact of emotional intelligence on job performance of paramedical employee's in public Vs private hospitals: a comparison. *Am. J. Multidiscipl. Res. Dev. (AJMRD)* 2(10), 38–45 (2020)

Ardebili, M.E., Naserbakht, M., Bernstein, C., Alazmani-Noodeh, F., Hakimi, H., Ranjbar, H.: Health-care providers experience of working during the COVID-19 pandemic: a qualitative study. *Am. J. Infect. Control* 49(5), 547–554 (2021)

Aria, M., Cuccurullo, C.: Bibliometrix: an R-tool for comprehensive science mapping analysis. *J. Informet.* 11(4), 959–975 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2017.08.007>

Ashton-James, C.E., McNeilage, A.G.: A mixed methods investigation of stress and wellbeing factors contributing to burnout and job satisfaction in a specialist small animal hospital. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 9, 942778 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2022.942778>

Barragán Martín, A.B., MoleroJurado, M.D.M., Pérez-Fuentes, M.D.C., SimónMárquez, M.D.M., Sisto, M., Gázquez Linares, J.J.: Published research on burnout in nursing in Spain in the last decade: bibliometric analysis. *Healthcare* 8(4), 478 (2020)

Bashir, A., Hanif, R.: Job satisfaction and burnout as outcome of workplace bullying among healthcare professionals. *Rawal Med. J.* 43(3), 405 (2018)

Cao, Y., Gao, L., Fan, L., Zhang, Z., Liu, X., Jiao, M., Li, Y., Zhang, S.: Effects of verbal violence on job satisfaction, work engagement and the mediating role of emotional exhaustion among health-care workers: a cross-sectional survey conducted in Chinese tertiary public hospitals. *BMJ Open* 13(3), 065918 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2022-065918>

Carvalho, C., Pinto, A., Oliveira, S., Matos, M.I., Santos-Costa, P.: COVID-19 pandemic's influence on the study of burnout: a bibliometric analysis. *J. Invest. Méd. (JIM)* 4(2), 49–63 (2023)

Cetinkaya, F., Akbulut, Z., Dur, N., Eryalcin, O., Korkmaz, M.: Analysis of job satisfaction and burnout level of nurses in different generations. *Int. J. Caring Sci.* 10(3), 1507–1513 (2017)

Chang, E., Cohen, J., Koethe, B., Smith, K., Bir, A.: Measuring job satisfaction among healthcare staff in the United States: a confirmatory factor analysis of the satisfaction of employees in health care (SEHC) survey. *Int. J. Qual. Health Care* 29(2), 262–268 (2017)

Chaudhuri, A., Paul, S., Mondal, T., Goswami, A.: A study of perceived stress, burnout, and job satisfaction of doctors and nonmedical staff in a medical college of West Bengal during COVID-19 pandemic. *Med. J. Dr. DY Patil Univ.* 14(6), 617–622 (2021)

Chen, X., Lun, Y., Yan, J., Hao, T., Weng, H.: Discovering thematic change and evolution of utilizing social media for healthcare research. *BMC Med. Inform. Decis. Mak.* 19(2), 39–53 (2019)

Cobo, M.J., Martínez, M.Á., Gutiérrez-Salcedo, M., Fujita, H., Herrera-Viedma, E.: 25 years at knowledge-based systems: a bibliometric analysis. *Knowl.-Based Syst.* 80, 3–13 (2015)

de Las Heras-Rosas, C., Herrera, J., Rodríguez-Fernández, M.: Organisational commitment in healthcare systems: a bibliometric analysis. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 18(5), 2271 (2021)

de Oliveira, D.G., da Cunha Reis, A., de Melo Franco, I., Braga, A.L.: Exploring global research trends in burnout among nursing professionals: a bibliometric analysis. *Healthcare* 9(12), 1680 (2021)

de-la-Fuente-Robles, Y.M., Ricoy-Cano, A.J., Albín-Rodríguez, A.P., López-Ruiz, J.L., Espinilla-Estévez, M.: Past, present and future of research on wearable technologies for healthcare: a bibliometric analysis using Scopus. *Sensors* 22(22), 8599 (2022)

Ding, X., Yang, Z.: Knowledge mapping of platform research: a visual analysis using VOSviewer and CiteSpace. *Electron. Commer. Res.* 22, 787 (2022)

Dinibutun, S.R.: Factors affecting burnout and job satisfaction of physicians at public and private hospitals: a comparative analysis. *J. Healthc. Leadersh.* 15, 387–401 (2023)

Doolittle, B.R.: Burnout, compassion fatigue, and job satisfaction among hospital chaplains: a systematic review. *Res. Soc. Sci. Study Relig.* 26, 180–197 (2015)

Dubale, B.W., Friedman, L.E., Chemali, Z., Denninger, J.W., Mehta, D.H., Alem, A., Fricchione, G.L., Dossett, M.L., Gelaye, B.: Systematic review of burnout among healthcare providers in sub-Saharan Africa. *BMC Public Health* 19(1), 1–20 (2019)

Edú-Valsania, S., Laguía, A., Moriano, J.A.: Burnout: a review of theory and measurement. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 19(3), 1780 (2022)

Fatima, S., Tandon, P., Singh, A.B.: Current state and future directions of sustainability and innovation in finance: a bibliometric review. *Int. J. Syst. Assur. Eng. Manag.* 15(5), 1591–1614 (2024)

Florek-Paszkowska, A.K., Hoyos-Vallejo, C.A.: A comprehensive bibliometric analysis and future research directions in the nexus of sustainable business practices and turnover intention. *Clean. Responsib. Consum.* 11, 100146 (2023)

Friganović, A., Selič, P., Ilić, B.: Stress and burnout syndrome and their associations with coping and job satisfaction in critical care nurses: a literature review. *Psychiatr. Danub.* 31(suppl. 1), 21–31 (2019).

Galanis, P., Moisoglou, I., Katsiroumpa, A., Vraka, I., Siskou, O., Konstantakopoulou, O., Meimeti, E., Kaitelidou, D.: Increased job burnout and reduced job satisfaction for nurses compared to other healthcare workers after the COVID-19 pandemic. *Nurs. Rep.* 13(3), 1090–1100 (2023)

Garcia, C.D.L., Abreu, L.C.D., Ramos, J.L.S., Castro, C.F.D.D., Smiderle, F.R.N., Santos, J.A.D., Bezerra, I.M.P.: Influence of burnout on patient safety: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medicina* 55(9), 553 (2019)

Gray, P., Senabe, S., Naicker, N., Kgalamono, S., Yassi, A., Spiegel, J.M.: Workplace-based organizational interventions promoting mental health and happiness among healthcare workers: a realist review. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 16(22), 4396 (2019)

Hameed, F.B., Hussain, A., Ali, S.: Compassion fatigue, compassion satisfaction, burnout and its associated factors among nurses working in critical care area of tertiary care hospital, Karachi, Pakistan. *Liaquat Natl. J. Primary Care* 5(2), 66–72 (2023)

Huang, C., Yang, C., Wang, S., Wu, W., Su, J., Liang, C.: Evolution of topics in education research: a systematic review using bibliometric analysis. *Educ. Rev.* 72(3), 281–297 (2020)

Jia, S., Yu, B., Feng, C., Jia, P., Xu, P., Yang, S.: Occupational burnout, flourishing and job satisfaction among HIV/AIDS healthcare workers in Western China: a network analysis. *BMC Psychiatry* 23(1), 560 (2023)

Johnson, J., Hall, L.H., Berzins, K., Baker, J., Melling, K., Thompson, C.: Mental healthcare staff well-being and burnout: a narrative review of trends, causes, implications, and recommendations for future interventions. *Int. J. Mental Health Nurs.* 27(1), 20–32 (2017)

- Kelly, M., Soles, R., Garcia, E., Kundu, I.: Job stress, burnout, work-life balance, well-being, and job satisfaction among pathology residents and fellows. *Am. J. Clin. Pathol.* 153(4), 449–469 (2020)
- Khamisa, N., Oldenburg, B., Peltzer, K., Ilic, D.: Work related stress, burnout, job satisfaction and general health of nurses. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 12(1), 652–666 (2015)
- Khamisa, N., Peltzer, K., Ilic, D., Oldenburg, B.: Effect of personal and work stress on burnout, job satisfaction and general health of hospital nurses in South Africa. *Health SA Gesondheid* 22, 252–258 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hsag.2016.10.001>
- Klein, J., Frie, K.G., Blum, K., Von dem Knesebeck, O.: Psychosocial stress at work and perceived quality of care among clinicians in surgery. *BMC Health Serv. Res.* 11, 109–117 (2011)
- Kroft, S.H.: Well-being, burnout, and the clinical laboratory. *Am. J. Clin. Pathol.* 153(4), 422–424 (2020)
- Kulkarni, A.V., Aziz, B., Shams, I., Busse, J.W.: Comparisons of citations in Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar for articles published in general medical journals. *JAMA* 302(10), 1092–1096 (2009)
- Larasati, A., Aryanto, D.B.: Job-hopping and the determinant factors. In: 5 ASEAN Conference on Psychology, Counselling, and Humanities (ACPCH 2019), pp. 54–56. Atlantis Press (2020). <https://www.atlantispublishing.com/proceedings/acpch-19/125932598>. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.200120.011>
- Lee, J.: Emotional labor, burnout and job satisfaction among Korean clinical nurses. *Med.-Legal Update* 19(1), 446 (2019)
- Leo, C.G., Sabina, S., Tumolo, M.R., Bodini, A., Ponzini, G., Sabato, E., Mincarone, P.: Burnout among healthcare workers in the COVID 19 era: a review of the existing literature. *Front. Public Health* 9, 1661 (2021)
- Lluch, C., Galiana, L., Doménech, P., Sansó, N.: The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on burnout, compassion fatigue, and compassion satisfaction in healthcare personnel: a systematic review of the literature published during the first year of the pandemic. *Healthcare* 10(2), 364 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10020364>
- Lu, H., Zhao, Y., While, A.: Job satisfaction among hospital nurses: a literature review. *Int. J. Nurs.Stud.* 94, 21–31 (2019)
- Maia, S.C., de Benedicto, G.C., do Prado, J.W., Robb, D.A., de Almeida Bispo, O.N., de Brito, M.J.: Mapping the literature on credit unions: a bibliometric investigation grounded in Scopus and Web of Science. *Scientometrics* 120, 929–960 (2019)
- Moscu, C.A., Marina, V., Dragomir, L., Anghel, A.D., Anghel, M.: The impact of burnout syndrome on job satisfaction among emergency department nurses of emergency clinical county hospital “Sfântul Apostol Andrei” of Galati, Romania. *Medicina* 58(11), 1516 (2022)

Mühl, D.D., de Oliveira, L.: A bibliometric and thematic approach to agriculture 4.0. *Heliyon* 8(5), e09369 (2022)

O'Brien, L., Mitchell, D., Skinner, E.H., Haas, R., Ghaly, M., McDermott, F., May, K., Haines, T.: What makes weekend allied health services effective and cost-effective (or not) in acute medical and surgical wards? Perceptions of medical, nursing, and allied health workers. *BMC Health Serv. Res.* 17(1), 1–13 (2017)

Page, M.J., McKenzie, J.E., Bossuyt, P.M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T.C., Mulrow, C.D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J.M., Akl, E.A., Brennan, S.E. and Chou, R.: The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 372 (2021)

Passas, I.: Bibliometric analysis: the main steps. *Encyclopedia* 4(2), 1014 (2024)

Platis, C., Reklitis, P., Zimeras, S.: Relation between job satisfaction and job performance in healthcare services. *Proc. Soc. Behav. Sci.* 175, 480–487 (2015)

Porkodi, S., AlZadjali, A.S., AlRahbi, F.S., AlNabhani, Y.M.: Effect of cultural intelligence (CI) on patient care services in private hospitals at Muscat governorate. *Eur. J. Bus. Manag. Res.* 7(1), 304–311 (2022) Prado-Gascó, V., Giménez-Espert, M.D.C., De Witte, H.: Job insecurity in nursing: a bibliometric analysis. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 18(2), 663 (2021)

Rad, A.M.M., De Moraes, A.: Factors affecting employees' job satisfaction in public hospitals: implications for recruitment and retention. *J. Gen. Manag.* 34(4), 51–66 (2009)

Rauf, A., Muhammad, N., Mahmood, H., Aftab, M.: Healthcare service quality: a systematic review based on PRISMA guidelines. *Int. J. Qual. Reliab. Manag.* 42(3), 837–850 (2024)

Ruiz-Fernández, M.D., Ramos-Pichardo, J.D., Ibáñez-Masero, O., Cabrera-Troya, J., Carmona-Rega, M.I., Ortega-Galán, N.M.: Compassion fatigue, burnout, compassion satisfaction and perceived stress in healthcare professionals during the COVID-19 health crisis in Spain. *J. Clin. Nurs.* 29(21–22), 4321–4330 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.15469>

Saha, S., Saha, S.K., Jha, A., Kumar, S.: Job satisfaction among health-care practitioners: a bibliometric analysis. *J. Radiol. Nurs.* 44, 68 (2024)

Salleh, N.Z.M., Abdullah, M., Ali, A., Faisal, F., Nor, R.M.: Research trends, developments, and future perspectives in brand attitude: a bibliometric analysis utilizing the Scopus database (1944–2021). *Heliyon* 9(1), e12765 (2023)

Selič-Zupančič, P., Klemenc-Ketiš, Z., OnukTement, S.: The impact of psychological interventions with elements of mindfulness on burnout and well-being in healthcare professionals: a systematic review. *J. Multidiscipl. Healthc.* 16, 1821–1831 (2023)

Soares, J.P., Lopes, R.H., de Souza Mendonça, P.B., Silva, C.R.D.V., Rodrigues, C.C.F.M., de Castro, J.L.: Use of the Maslach burnout inventory among public health care professionals: scoping review. *JMIR Mental Health* 10(1), e44195 (2023)

Soumyaja, D., Sowmya, C.S., Joy, A.: Emotional labour and job satisfaction of nurses working in public hospitals: testing the mediating role of burnout and moderating role of gender. *Int. J. Work Organ. Emot.* 13(2), 152–171 (2022)

Sweileh, W.M.: Research trends and scientific analysis of publications on burnout and compassion fatigue among healthcare providers. *J. Occup. Med. Toxicol.* 15, 1–10 (2020)

Terry, D.L., Mathews, D.P.: Technology-assisted supplemental work among rural medical providers: impact on burnout, stress, and job satisfaction. *J. Healthc. Manag.* 66(6), 451–458 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1097/JHM-D-19-00182>

Trockel, M., Bohman, B., Lesure, E., Hamidi, M.S., Welle, D., Roberts, L., Shanafelt, T.: A brief instrument to assess both burnout and professional fulfillment in physicians: reliability and validity, including correlation with self-reported medical errors, in a sample of resident and practicing physicians. *Acad. Psychiatry* 42(1), 11–24 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40596-017-0849-3>

Tziner, A., Rabenu, E., Radomski, R., Belkin, A.: Work stress and turnover intentions among hospital physicians: the mediating role of burnout and work satisfaction. *Revista De Psicología Del Trabajo Y De Las Organizaciones* 31(3), 207–213 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rpto.2015.05.001>

Ulfa, M., Azuma, M., Steiner, A.: Burnout status of healthcare workers in the world during the peak period of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Front. Psychol.* 13, 952783 (2022)

Urkude, S.V., Sahoo, D.: Systematic review on sustainable healthcare practices: a bibliometric approach. In: *International Conference on Computation of Artificial Intelligence & Machine Learning*, pp. 74–85. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham (2024)

van Mol, M.M.C., Kompanje, E.J.O., Benoit, D.D., Bakker, J., Nijkamp, M.D.: The prevalence of compassion fatigue and burnout among healthcare professionals in intensive care units: a systematic review. *Plos One* 10(8), e0136955 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0136955>

Vuong, B., Tung, D., Tushar, H., Quan, T., Giao, H.: Determinates of factors influencing job satisfaction and organizational loyalty. *Manag. Sci. Lett.* 11(1), 203–212 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2020.8.014>

Zaidan, A.A., Alnoor, A., Albahri, O.S., Mohammed, R.T., Alamoodi, A.H., Albahri, A.S., Zaidan, B.B., Garfan, S., Hameed, H., Al-Samarraay, M.S., Malik, R.Q.: Review of artificial neural.